

DIGITAL EDUCATION – A CRITICAL ANALYZE OF WEB APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Purpose – critically analyze 4 learning applications/platforms

Methodology/approach - comparison in pairs alongside analytic hierarchy process (AHP) have been used

Findings – a digital application that is close to covering all the user's needs from a cloud learning perspective

Research limitations/implications – there were selected only 4 learning applications because of the limited number of platforms that are available and are able to cover most of the users' needs

Practical implications – analyze the affordability, general aspects, what fields do the applications/platforms cover, how user friendly are them and how efficient are to the users, analyzing in deep the downsides and upsides

Originality/value – helping users decide which application is best suited for each individual, given criteria's like: affordability, domains, accessibility, requirements and efficiency

Key words: Education, Digital, Applications

1. Introduction

For several years, Internet of Things (IoT) and cloud computing, have been transforming the IT environment, working together and managing to make the life of users more comfortable when using software and hardware products. The cloud environment has become important because of the motivation to improve data processing and storage resources to be done more efficiently, being cost-effective and offering multiple resources. There is a high importance for the costs of businesses to be reduced and the work productivity to improve.

In the first part of this paper there is presented an overview of IoT, cloud computing, virtual learning methods and services. The study has been conducted on over 80 papers identified and analyzed, filtered by criteria's such as: relevance to the subject and covered subdomains. A number of 40 papers have been preserved and were divided in subdomains like: IoT, cloud computing, digital education. From a list of cloud applications, the relevant ones were selected and studied, looking at the downsides and upsides of them. For the research purpose in the establishment selection criteria for a digital application that is close to covering all the user's needs, there were used 2 methods: the comparison in pairs and the analytic hierarchy process (AHP).

2. Background

2.1 IoT influence

In the present, connected devices are attracting a significant amount of attention among researches and worldwide institutes responsible with cyber security. Nobody knows how the future will look like with all

these devices interconnected and actively involved in our daily routine. Alongside IoT another domain that is growing day by day is the cloud environment. It has to be mentioned that IoT and cloud are interconnected and work together very well, as one has the equipment's to interconnect things, the other has the modern infrastructure and services. The advantage that IoT is offering comes with the connectivity freedom on using supported technologies like wireless, Bluetooth, data or mobile networks. (Ray, 2016) Another advantage of IoT devices is the capability to adapt to changes implemented on the operating conditions, user's context even on the connectivity of the network. For example, cameras could switch from lower resolution to higher resolution when any movement is detected. Also, IoT devices have self-configuring capacities allowing the devices to work together and provide high functionality. These platforms influence domains like data management, system management, applications development, analytics, deployment, education, medicine.

2.2 Cloud environment

The cloud environment has become important because of the motivation to improve data processing and storage resources to be done more efficiently, being cost-effective and offering multiple resources. There is a high importance for the costs of businesses to be reduced and the work productivity to improve.

The main distribution models from cloud environment, the services and the applications offered are presented in Table 1: Distribution models, services and applications used in cloud.

Table 1: Distribution models, services and applications used in cloud.

Distribution models	SAAS	PAAS	IAAS
Definition	Software as a service	Platform as a service	Infrastructure as a service
Services offered	Email Productivity tools	Security Development of applications Management of databases	Network Servers Management
Applications used	IBM Oracle Google apps	Windows azure Amazon	Cisco Microsoft

The distribution models that are used when implementing cloud products are: SAAS, PAAS, and IAAS.

Software as a service (SAAS) is referring to a software licensing model where software is licensed on a subscription and is centrally hosted being accessed by users via a web browser. (Nabil, 2010)

Platform as a service (PAAS) makes available to users a platform where there can develop, run and manage applications without the expensive of hardware components and infrastructure.

Infrastructure as a service (IAAS) is the delivery of the network infrastructure, servers, storage and the software from these resources into a service. (Overton & Dr Dixon, 2016)

2.3 Digital Education

With the help of IoT and cloud environment a new type of education has been growing and evolving in the past years. Digital education is an environment that is gathering a number of learning methods like: eLearning, iLearning, mLearning.

Following the general change of people's habits and the world's job market structure, the education sector has gone through a large-scale transformation over the last few years. Cisco systems, the first leaders in developing internet and networking technologies that changed the way peoples work, interact and live, were the first ones focusing on eLearning in the 1990's. (L.C. & R.J., 2002)

ELearning is short for electronic learning and can be described as the use of web-based technology tools and enables the form of distance and non-contact education. ELearning promotes distance education and facilitates the education content.

ILearning has the same principles and concepts as eLearning. It is short from internet-based learning and it can be defined as a process of searching data online and the learner stores the information found and will use that information. (Fariborz & Ehsan, 2014)

Mlearning refers to mobile learning, focusing on using mobile technology for learning purposes. It is a new technology and it allows people that have a smartphone/tablet/laptop and an internet connection to obtain learning materials.

3. Digital education discussions

Digital education is already implemented in several schools but in its full complexity will remain a big challenge in traditional formal educational settings.

The supply of online education needs to be understood within the context of the educational environment. Online delivery can be very effective at the provision of domain knowledge and can assist with the development of communication skills and to extent with interpersonal skills and the co-construction of knowledge. However, the provision of work experience of higher-level interpersonal skills presents a significant challenge for online education as currently delivered. (Khare & Hurst, 2018)

There is a debate about the quality of online versus on-campus digital education that continues to rage. While some resist the move to virtual campuses and learning, it is hard to deny the preferences of a connected population who seek increasingly flexible, accessible learning opportunities, course materials, classrooms, faculty, and associated services anytime and from anywhere.

Unlike the online education courses of the past 20 years, today's online courses are of much higher quality and are available to be consumed anywhere, at any time and at any speed. A group of online education digital platforms have been launched in the past years to deliver these courses. Companies will either partner with these digital platform providers to build courses and credentialed learning paths or they will build their own platforms. (Auer & Tsiatsos, 2018)

3.1 IoT in education

Internet has changed the way people interact and education has not been immune to this change, which has created new forms of interaction between teachers and students that helps to improve the teaching and learning process and expands the context in which students learn. Technology is one of the elements that have strongly influenced education in recent years, particularly since the Internet boom. Taking technology as one of its tools, education is changing from a model by which knowledge is only transmitted to one where it is presented in an active and collaborative manner, seeking to improve the processes of teaching and learning. (Marquez, Villanueva, Zeida, & Garcia, 2016)

The Internet of Things (IoT) is influencing the education field and allows Internet based communications to happen between physical objects, sensors and controllers, changing educational institutions massively. By embedding sensors in objects and integrating cloud computing and applications, augmented reality, wearable technologies and big data in this platform, different parameters of the educational environment can be measured and analyzed to provide useful information. It also has created a new interaction between people and the environment in educational organization. (Maryam & Siavosh, 2016)

For users, students and employees of different companies it is easier to access materials and obtain information about new technologies. Internet of things in education is offering innovation, remote connectivity and helping students, employees, developers in testing and creating new technologies and new learning processes. Figure 1 represents the influence of IOT in education, in people's lives and in technology.

Figure 1: Influence of IOT in education, in people's lives and in technology

4. Research methodology

The objective of the research is to critically analyze 4 learning applications/platforms, covering affordability, general aspects, what domains do they influence, how user friendly are they and how efficient are to users. By using a pairwise comparison and a matrix diagram it can be obtain a local objectivity, on each application, at a certain moment, by a certain work team. The results may vary if the method is applied under different conditions. We will be compiling a list of elements to be ranked and arranging them in a matrix square $n \times n$. Each element will be compared with all the others, going along the lines: depending on the importance perceived by the team, by mutual agreement and 10 points are distributed on each element of the comparison. The notes on each line are summed up and the final ranking of the hierarchical elements is established. The comparison in pairs alongside analytic hierarchy process (AHP) will be used in the establishment selection criteria for a digital application that is close to covering all the user's needs.

4.1 Analyzing previous works

In table 2 are presented a number of most relevant papers analyzed that are influencing, helping and trying to implement correctly and with ease of access the digital education process. From the first paper we can observe that the impact is directed exactly to the users (teachers and students) helping them in the online learning process and presentation. The second paper is using learning platforms to help the people that want to learn different skills and to get specialized in key domains. In the 3rd paper a new way of thinking has been presented the "Computational thinking" that could become a cultural technique and a mutual approach to a refined working definition. Paper number 4 explores the online educational process focused in the business domain looking to increase efficiency and effectiveness of the users using this technique. In the last paper of the table studies the effect of the Internet of Things (IoT) on an Education Business Model.

The focus of the research will be to study the platforms that have been launched in the last years to deliver online courses. These are: UDEMY, LYNDA, UDACITY and EDX

Each of these platforms will be studied by general aspects, what fields do they cover and how user friendly they can be.

Table 2: Papers analyzed, research and impact

Authors	Paper summary	Research purpose	Impact
(Marquez, Villanueva, Zeida, & Garcia, 2016)	With the help of IOT this paper introduces a new model for digital learning	Developing an Integration model of virtual academic communities with the help of IOT	Helping Students and teachers that are learning in classes Helping teachers understand better the on-line learning process
(Auer & Tsiatsos, 2018)	Oriented on the development process of IOT in education	Studying learning platforms like: UDEMY, LYNDA, UDACITY, EDX, HBS	Over 100 people are using these platforms daily to learn different skills and to get specialized in key domains that can help the work environment
(Don, Bottino, Lewin, & Sanchez, 2018)	Computational Thinking on the Way to a Cultural Technique	Debate on computational thinking from different perspectives: one of a teacher and the other view is from a reflective software engineer	Computational thinking could become a cultural technique and a mutual approach to a refined working definition
(Khare & Hurst, 2018)	Online business education	The demand side consists of the demonstrated needs of organizations desiring the skills and knowledge of business graduates whether for a degree, diploma, or upgrading.	The efficiency and effectiveness of online provision will likely prove to be central tenets of the value proposition considered by potential consumers.
(Maryam & Siavosh, 2016)	The Effect of the Internet of Things (IoT) on an Education Business Model	Integrating cloud computing, augmented reality, wearable technologies and big data in this platform, different parameters of the educational environment can be measured and analyzed	This platform has changed the Education Business Model and added new value propositions in organizations

4.2 Digital education platforms

In table 3 are highlighted the general aspects of each platform, the affordability and the discount packages, the domains covered and at what level where the requirements of a user experience fulfilled.

Starting with Udemy, it can be observed the high advantages offered in the affordability sector, with 30 days free subscription and a lot of discounts on different course packages. Also, the availability to learn on your schedule anywhere anytime is something to consider. Because of the high availability to learn and the discounts provided, UDEMY obtained a high rating in user experience.

LYNDA, the second platform offers digital education for people, business, schools and government organizations. The courses provided are the same as UDEMY, but unfortunately for the residential users no discounts are in place. With the same courses offered and affordability issues the rating obtained will be LOW.

UDACITY is the platform that offers multiple discounts and it is the only one from all 4. It is oriented on the tech field and strongly using IOT in the services provided. The small downside is that courses are tech oriented and fields like medicine, education, business are neglected. However, because of the vast courses provided in the tech fields and the discounts offered a HIGH rating is obtained.

The last platform is EDX, and from all it is the most complex one. Offering over 2500 online courses it has the largest database compared with the others and covering all the domains from tech, to medicine, to education and business. However, the downside is that no discounts are applied on any course and affordability has a big percentage in the users view so the MEDIUM rating has been given. All these platforms are ideal for digital education offering lots of training programs, resources, software's, discounts, and helping people developing and growing in different sectors of work fields.

Table 3: Digital learning platform

Platform	General aspects	Affordability, discount packages	Courses / domains covered	User requirements where met? (Low, Medium, High)
UDEMY	Availability to learn on your schedule anywhere anytime	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 20 Euros discount from 100 Euros - 30 days free trial - if not satisfied the price paid will be refunded 	Development, business, IT, design, photography, marketing	High
LYNDA	Offer flexible, cost-effective group memberships for business, school, or government organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One Free month - No other discounts 	Development, business, IT, design, education, government, developer	Low
UDACITY	Learn the latest tech skills to propel your career	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 50% discounts on monthly and 3 months payments 	Cloud computing, Data science, business, programming	High
EDX	Access 2500+ online courses from 140 institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No discounts 	Development, business, IT, design, education, government, developer, Cloud, computing, data science, business, etc.	Medium

4.3 Research using comparison in pairs and AHP

In the final part of the paper for the research purpose there will be used 2 methods, the comparison in pairs and the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) in the establishment selection criteria for a digital application that is close to covering all the user's needs. The AHP was developed by Thomas L. Satty in the 1970s and it's a method used in fields like industry, business, education and other mores and has the particularity in group decision making. It uses math and psychology and is a good method for organizing and analyzing complex decisions. It provides a rational framework for a needed decision by quantifying its criteria and alternative options, and for relating those elements to the overall goal. (passagetechology.com, 2020). Figure 2 that was generated by Satty presents the fundamental scale for pairwise comparisons for assigning the weights.

The goal is for a user to decide which application is best, given criteria's like: affordability, domains, accessibility, requirements and efficiency. Affordability refers to the price that the courses cost. Accessibility represents that it can be accessed from all countries of the world and no restrictions are applied. Requirements represents that it can be accessed from all types of smart devices. And efficiency, represents the learning skills that should be gained after using the learning applications /websites.

Table 4 presents how important is each criteria to another and are given importance number from the fundamental scale. All the rows with the same name intersection will receive automatically a 1. In table 5, the fractional value will be converted to decimal value and on each row starting from upwards to bottom and the total sum will be calculated. After obtaining the total sum each criteria will be divided by that total number obtained, for example in the affordability column we will divide 1/1.65, 0.2/1.65, 0.25/1.65 and finally 0.2/1.65.

Intensity of Importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two elements contribute equally to the objective
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgment slightly favor one element over another
5	Strong importance	Experience and judgment strongly favor one element over another
7	Very strong importance	One element is favored very strongly over another; its dominance is demonstrated in practice
9	Extreme importance	The evidence favoring one element over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation
Intensities of 2, 4, 6, and 8 can be used to express intermediate values. Intensities 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, etc. can be used for elements that are very close in importance.		

Figure 2: AHP fundamental scale

Table 4: pair-wise comparison

	Affordability	Domains	Accessibility	Efficiency
Affordability	1	5	4	5
Domains	1/5	1	3	7
Accessibility	1/4	3	1	5
Efficiency	1/5	1/7	4	1

Table 5: Fractional value and total sum on each row

	Affordability	Domains	Accessibility	Efficiency
Affordability	1	5	4	5
Domains	0.2	1	3	7
Accessibility	0.25	3	1	5
Efficiency	0.2	0.142	4	1
Sum	1.65	9.142	12	18

The result will provide the normalized pair-wise in table 6. In the criteria weights/priorities are calculated all the values in the row from left to right and divided to 4, the number of criteria's. We can observe that when choosing an application the cost price is the main priority with a percentage of 44%.

Table 6: normalized pair-wise comparison

	Affordability	Domains	Accessibility	Efficiency	Criteria weights/ Priorities
Affordability	0.6060	0.5469	0.3333	0.2777	0.4409
Domains	0.1212	0.1093	0.25	0.3888	0.2173
Accessibility	0.1515	0.3281	0.8333	0.2777	0.3976
Efficiency	0.1212	0.0155	0.3333	0.0555	0.1313

Table 7: Fractional value and total sum of affordability on each application

Affordability	UDEMY	LYNDA	UDACITY	EDX
UDEMY	1	3	4	7
LYNDA	0.333	1	3	5
UDACITY	0.25	0.333	1	5
EDX	0.142	0.2	0.2	1
Sum	1.725	4.533	8.2	18

The next table demonstrates the weight of each application against the affordability criteria and it is presented the value converted to decimal and the total sum. After obtaining the total sum each criteria will be divided by that total number obtained and the result will provide the normalized pair-wise presented in table 8 and the application with the high percentage of affordability. In the criteria weights/priorities are calculated all the values in the row from left to right and divided to 4, the number of criteria's.

Table 8: Normalized pair-wise comparison applications/affordability

Affordability	UDEMY	LYNDA	UDACITY	EDX	Criteria weights/ Priorities
UDEMY	0.5797	0.6618	0.4878	0.3888	0.529
LYNDA	0.1930	0.2206	0.3658	0.2777	0.264
UDACITY	0.1449	0.734	0.1219	0.2777	0.319
EDX	0.0823	0.441	0.2432	0.0555	0.205

The user's best decision based off their priorities is the UDEMY application with a priority percentage of 52.9%. It's also the most affordable one from all the applications. The next application is UDACITY with a 31.9%, offering also discounts and courses for cloud computing, data science, business and programming. LYNDA obtained 26.4% in the user priorities, offering one month discount and opportunities in fields like development, business, IT, design, education, government, developer. EDX is the most complex application from all covered in this paper and it has access to 2500+ online courses from 140 institutions but from priorities perspective it has the lowest percentage, 20% in users preferences.

5. Conclusions

Globalization has put digital education at the centre of the economic and social agenda, emphasizing that the integration of technology with education is considered today a qualifying factor for success. Providing agility and strategic fit for business education's role in the modern world.

The appeal to study online comes from several incentives: the provision of flexibility, the possibility of gaining a credential from a world-renowned university to compliment on-the-job experience, and the added-value of networking with fellow students and co-workers from all around the world.

Digital learning is helping and emerging as a useful resource in education, influencing and helping the main fields of the world economy. It can be considered that the learning experience will be improved consistently in the years to come as this method is just at the beginning and it is growing day by day. People will need to be prepared to invest in this learning technologies because they come with a cost if they are not supported by an institution or business company. On the other hand, by using the power of the cloud learning technologies, students and teacher will be able to use the tools they need in a limited amount of time with no costs and from different locations. Delivery of education carries great potential, but it must be done in awareness of challenges with the right infrastructure and cost effective. In present times, a large amounts of companies, websites and applications are offering user's availability to learn on schedule anywhere anytime.

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